

Resilient UAV Routes for Emergency Services Using 5G Networks

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Abstract. This study proposes an advanced system for managing urban air transport during emergency scenarios using 5G networks as an alternative positioning system in dense urban environments, where the GNSS signals are often affected. The system is evaluated within a realistic scenario, in a predefined clustering of the existing cellular network in Valencia (Spain), assuming all stations are equipped with 5G technology. It dynamically generates resilient routes connecting a strategic point (A) with an emergency random point (B), prioritizing accuracy across congested urban areas. The core of the route planning algorithm relies on an accuracy metric, the Cramér Rao Lower Bound (CRLB), and incorporates dynamic base station selection and multilateration techniques to improve robustness. Furthermore, the system implicitly integrates inter-cluster soft handover procedures, ensuring continuity and precision as the UAV transitions across network regions. The simulated results use the Positioning Reference Signals (PRS) from 5G, comparing the Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) and route performance between direct and three optimized paths, using trajectories with a fixed-point A and a random point B . The results demonstrate the system's ability to improve the precision and generate adaptive air routes for emergency support in complex urban environments without GNSS systems.

Keywords: 5G, Positioning UAV, Urban Air Transport, UAV emergency routes, PRS, CRLB, MLAT

1 Introduction

The rapid advances in Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs) have revolutionized the emergency response, enabling rapid access to inaccessible urban areas where conventional ground systems are delayed by traffic congestion [1,2,3]. However, UAVs rely heavily on GNSS navigation, which is susceptible to interference, multipath, and spoofing attacks that compromise positioning accuracy [4,5]. These vulnerabilities are critical in emergency missions such as police response, where maintaining high precision while minimizing flight time is crucial

To address these challenges, we propose a resilient, real-time trajectory generation system based on a 5G Multilateration (MLAT) infrastructure using

Time Difference of Arrival (TDOA) [6]. Our approach integrates an optimized 8-neighbor Dijkstra algorithm with a cost function based on the Cramér-Rao Lower Bound (CRLB) to prioritize paths with maximum positioning reliability [6]. The system incorporates angular constraints and an adaptive smoothing procedure to ensure that the resulting emergency routes are energy-efficient and free of abrupt maneuvers. Evaluated via PX4 SITL simulations in Valencia (Spain), the system demonstrates a superior balance between positioning error (RMSE), trajectory length, and flight time, providing a robust framework for mission-critical urban air mobility.

2 Methodology

Path planning in urban environments must balance energy consumption and flight time while avoiding sudden maneuvers [7,8]. While Dijkstra’s algorithm is a standard for shortest-path estimation [9], traditional four-neighbor grids often produce orthogonal, difficult-to-follow trajectories for UAVs. To ensure smoother, more resilient flight paths, our system implements an eight-neighbor connectivity model (diagonal movements) integrated with the 5G network infrastructure.

The study utilizes a 5×5 km simulation area in Valencia (Spain) with 92 5G-capable base stations (gNBs) organized into clusters [6,10]. The positioning workflow begins with a PRS transmission, from which the UAV determines the Time of Arrival (TOA) [11,12]. These measurements are processed in the Core Network using Multilateration (MLAT) based on Time Difference of Arrival (TDOA):

2.1 5G Positioning System

The simulation utilizes 92 5G-capable base stations (gNBs) within a 5×5 km area in Valencia, organized into clusters for positioning [6,10] (Fig. 1a). The positioning workflow begins with a PRS transmission to determine the Time of Arrival (TOA) at the UAV [11,12]. These measurements are processed in the Core Network via MLAT, where gNBs are dynamically selected based on signal power and DOP [10]. The resulting positioning reliability is mapped as a CRLB heatmap with 10 m resolution (Fig. 1b), which serves as the cost map for route optimization [6].

2.2 MLAT

Positioning is executed via Multilateration (MLAT) using TDOA values derived from TOA measurements:

$$T\widehat{DOA}_{i,1} = T\widehat{OA}_i - T\widehat{OA}_1 \quad (1)$$

3D coordinates are obtained through Least Squares, Taylor expansion, and regularization techniques to mitigate noise and ill-conditioned scenarios [6,10].

Fig. 1: Resulting clustering in Valencia and CRLB heat map with 10 m spatial resolution

To refine Z-axis estimation, gNBs with Angle of Arrival (AoA) capabilities are integrated. To ensure realism, a 50 ns RMS synchronization error is modeled in accordance with 3GPP specifications [13].

2.3 CRLB

The CRLB defines the theoretical minimum variance of any unbiased estimator, representing the limit of positioning accuracy. It is calculated as the inverse of the Fisher Information Matrix (FIM):

$$\text{CRLB}(\boldsymbol{\theta}) = \sqrt{\text{diag}(\mathbf{FIM}^{-1})} \quad (2)$$

To integrate this metric into the path planning process, the 5×5 km simulation area is discretized into a 10 m resolution grid [6,10]. Each cell is assigned its corresponding CRLB value, resulting in the cost map shown in Fig. 1b, which the algorithm uses to identify regions of maximum positioning reliability [6].

2.4 Routes Generator

Effective UAV path planning must balance flight time and energy consumption against operational constraints such as no-fly zones and positioning reliability [7,8]. While Dijkstra's algorithm is standard for cost minimization [9], traditional four-neighbor grids often produce abrupt maneuvers that hinder emergency response efficiency. To ensure smoother, resilient trajectories, we implement an eight-neighbor connectivity model integrated with a post-processing smoothing step [6]. The system operates on a 10 m resolution grid where each cell's CRLB value represents the local accuracy limit [6]. After mapping the initial (A) and destination (B) points to the grid, the edge weight w_{ij} between cell i and neighbor j is calculated as:

$$w_{ij} = \alpha \cdot \text{CRLB}(j) + \lambda \cdot \Phi(\theta_{ij}) \quad (3)$$

Where:

- α is a normalization factor ensuring that the CRLB contribution is within a comparable range to the angular penalty, given by $\alpha = \bar{d}/\overline{\text{CRLB}}$.
- $\Phi(\theta_{ij})$ is a function that increases with the angular deviation θ_{ij} relative to the previous travel direction.
- λ controls the trade-off between CRLB minimization and trajectory smoothness.

Also (3) is restricted for the condition $|\text{CRLB}(j) - \text{CRLB}_{min}| < \Delta\text{CRLB}$. This formulation allows the algorithm to prioritize straight-line continuation when CRLB values are similar, reducing zigzagging in regions with low CRLB variation. Effectively, the ΔCRLB acts as a tolerance band: if multiple neighbors offer comparable accuracy, the one with the smallest angular deviation is favored.

Adaptive Route Smoothing. Once the optimal route is obtained, an adaptive smoothing procedure is applied to reduce the number of waypoints, removing intermediate points that do not significantly change the global route direction, which means small oscillations and redundant waypoints under a maximum threshold of error CRLB_{max} . For each point P_i in the original path, the algorithm searches for the farthest reachable point P_j such that the direct segment $P_i \rightarrow P_j$ does not cross any cell where $\text{CRLB} > \text{CRLB}_{max}$. Among all valid candidates, the point P_j that maximizes the alignment score is selected:

$$\text{score}_j = \frac{P_i P_j \cdot P_i P_{end}}{\|P_i P_j\| \|P_i P_{end}\|} + k \left(1 - \frac{j-i}{n} \right) \quad (4)$$

Where:

- The first term measures the alignment of the segment $P_i P_j$ with the global direction of the path, encouraging straight continuation.
- The second term rewards longer jumps to reduce the number of intermediate waypoints, with k controlling the trade-off between straightness and waypoint reduction.
- n is the number of total points on the original route

This procedure is repeated iteratively until reaching the destination, producing a smoothed route with fewer waypoints, shorter total distance, and reduced steering effort for UAV controllers. This results in lower energy consumption and more dynamically feasible trajectories. A general overview of the functionality behind these improvements is presented in Algorithm 1, which provides a complete description of the proposed route generation method based on the CRLB.

3 Simulation Setup and Results

The system is evaluated in a 5×5 km urban area in Valencia (Spain) using the PX4 SITL environment [14]. Simulations model a police UAV flying at a fixed

Algorithm 1 Route Generation with CRLB Optimization and Smoothing

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Procedure GenerateSmoothedPath
Initialize open set with start
while open set is not empty do
  Select current  $\leftarrow$  node with minimum cost
  if current = goal then
    Break
  end if
  for each neighbor of current do
    Compute  $CRLB_{\min} \leftarrow \min(CRLB(\text{neighbors}))$ 
    if  $|CRLB(\text{neighbor}) - CRLB_{\min}| < \Delta_{CRLB}$  then
       $w \leftarrow \alpha \cdot CRLB(\text{neighbor}) + \lambda \cdot \Phi(\theta)$ 
    end if
    Update neighbor cost and parent if better
  end for
end while
path  $\leftarrow$  Reconstruct path from parents
SmoothPath(path):
for each  $P_i$  in path do
  Find farthest  $P_j$  such that  $CRLB$  along  $P_i \rightarrow P_j \leq CRLB_{\max}$  and
   $score_j = \frac{P_i P_j \cdot P_i P_{end}}{\|P_i P_j\| \|P_i P_{end}\|} + k \left(1 - \frac{j-i}{n}\right)$  is maximized
  Keep  $P_j$ , discard intermediate points
end for
Return smoothed path

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altitude of 100 m from a central station (A) to various emergency locations (B), including a bank, a park, and random points. Parameters follow 5G specifications [6,10] with a realistic 50 ns synchronization error [13]. We compare four methods: Direct, Dijkstra, Conditioned, and Conditioned Smoothed, across 100 Monte Carlo trials per route at a constant speed of 10 m/s, using RMSE, trajectory length, and flight time as performance metrics [6].

As shown in Fig. 2, the Dijkstra method achieves the highest positioning accuracy (lowest RMSE). However, the Direct route performs poorly, with positioning errors exceeding our proposed methods by more than 4 m [6]. While Dijkstra prioritizes accuracy, it often yields inefficient, hard-to-follow paths.

The radar charts in Fig. 3 highlight the operational trade-offs across the four methods. While the Dijkstra method achieves the highest positioning precision, it significantly increases both distance and travel time. Conversely, the Direct method minimizes these efficiency metrics but results in unacceptable RMSE values, compromising mission safety. The Conditioned Smoothed method provides the most effective balance, achieving significantly lower RMSE than the Direct path while maintaining shorter trajectories and faster response times than the standard Dijkstra approach.

To quantify overall performance, a normalized weighted score was calculated (Table 1) prioritizing travel time ($w_1 = 0.4$) and RMSE ($w_3 = 0.4$) over route length ($w_2 = 0.2$). The results indicate that the Conditioned Smoothed method

Fig. 2: RMSE XY for different Routes and methods

Fig. 3: Radar charts for the performance of the four path planning methods across three metrics, for three routes.

achieves the highest overall scores (0.64–0.75), demonstrating a superior balance between positioning accuracy and operational efficiency. Although the Dijkstra method minimizes RMSE, its high travel time and distance significantly reduce its final score. Conversely, the Direct method’s speed is penalized by unacceptable positioning errors. This confirms that the proposed trajectory generator provides the most resilient and effective balance for time-critical emergency missions in urban environments.

4 Conclusions

The results of this study demonstrate that combining CRLB-based cost formulation, angular penalization, and adaptive route smoothing enables the generation of resilient and operationally feasible UAV trajectories for urban emergency scenarios. Although the Dijkstra algorithm provides the lowest RMSE, this comes at the expense of longer routes and higher travel times. On the other hand, direct routes, while shorter, present considerably higher positioning errors, exceeding the proposed approach by more than 4 m on average.

Table 1: Parameter comparison and score assignment for each route.

Route	Type	Time [s]	Distance [m]	RMSE [m]	Score
1	Direct	383.41	3834.07	19.08	0.60
	Dijkstra	502.34	5023.35	14.92	0.40
	Conditioned	446.84	4468.31	15.29	0.64
	Conditioned Smoothed	415.48	4154.76	15.82	0.75
2	Direct	221.42	2214.16	19.34	0.60
	Dijkstra	290.49	2904.88	15.11	0.40
	Conditioned	261.25	2612.50	15.57	0.61
	Conditioned Smoothed	254.64	2546.40	15.84	0.64
3	Direct	143.00	1430.03	22.23	0.60
	Dijkstra	188.15	1881.45	15.76	0.40
	Conditioned	165.78	1657.81	16.36	0.66
	Conditioned Smoothed	158.46	1584.59	17.43	0.69

The Conditioned and Conditioned Smoothed routes offer a balanced compromise between accuracy and efficiency, as reflected by their higher weighted scores. The smoothed variant reduces the waypoints, leading to easier-to-follow paths for UAV and energy-efficient paths without increasing the RMS significantly. This makes it a promising option for time-critical missions where UAVs must fly in an emergency under strict operational constraints.

The proposed route generator based on 5G networks remains efficient and robust under realistic synchronization errors between gNBs, improving positioning accuracy. Also, it is important to mention that MLAT accuracy would increase significantly under perfect synchronization, consolidating this proposal as a viable alternative in environments where GNSS systems may be degraded or unavailable. Undoubtedly, this study enhances the reliability and usefulness of the proposed system for real deployments in U-space and urban air mobility frameworks.

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